

SEVERE ACCIDENT ANALYSIS OF SASPAM-SA DESIGN II LW-SMR DRY CONTAINMENT USING CONTAINMENTFOAM

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ABSTRACT

The Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project investigates the transferability of severe-accident knowledge and methods developed for large LWRs to Light-Water SMRs. While most SASPAM-SA partners rely on lumped-parameter tools (MELCOR, ASTEC, AC2), this work uses *containmentFOAM*, an open-source CFD add-on to OpenFOAM[®]-11, to complement those calculations with 3D, high-fidelity insight into the containment response of SASPAM-SA Design II, which features a containment with several passive safety systems. With that purpose, and using MELCOR data as boundary conditions, two different time windows of one of the SA sequences postulated in SASPAM-SA are analysed with *containmentFOAM*.

The first window covers the blowdown phase, where the large mass and energy release drives a rapid displacement and redistribution of the initial gases, with nitrogen transport to the Passive Suppression System (PSS) as the central aspect. The second window targets a later stage of the transient including the first significant hydrogen release, during which the hydrogen molar fraction rises from zero to about 0.1 and the flow field is governed by weak buoyancy-driven motions. In both windows, the local transport of non-condensables to the PSS end up determining the pressurization of the containment, that ultimately affect the severe accident progression. *containmentFOAM*'s simulations indicate that the blowdown phase quickly approaches a well-mixed atmosphere, suggesting that the added value of resolving 3D details is limited. In contrast, during the later time window, the weak buoyancy-driven flows sustain gas stratification, affecting the hydrogen distribution and its transport to the PSS.

KEYWORDS

SMR, CFD, *containmentFOAM*, OpenModelica

1. INTRODUCTION

The most recent energy outlooks published by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) postulates the deployment of up to 162 GW of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) by 2050 [1]. Among the concepts under consideration, Light Water SMRs (LW-SMRs) are the most likely ones to be deployed in the near term. They generally share key characteristics with currently operating large LWRs, while incorporating evolutionary design features that provide safety benefits and reinforce the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) principles [2,3]. Nevertheless, the path from conceptualization [4] to the licensed concept [5] of a reactor is complex, effort-intensive, and time-consuming, always involving numerous interactions between designers and regulators. Moreover, even for plants with advanced features strengthening DiD levels 1–3, regulators require independent provisions for Severe Accident (SA) prevention and mitigation to be incorporated in the design (DiD level 4). Consequently, scenarios that could lead to a SA must be postulated and studied deterministically (see [2] for details). In this context, the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project [6], coordinated by ENEA (Italy), addresses the identification of potential postulated SA

sequences for two generic concepts representative of a range of LW-SMRs. The SASPAM-SA Design-I features a generic integral Pressurised Water Reactors (i-PWR) of about 60 MWe embedded in a containment submerged in a pool, whereas Design-II consists of a generic 300 MWe i-PWR with a containment and several passive systems. The postulated SA sequences for each design are summarised in [6] for completeness.

Aligned with SASPAM-SA evaluation of the applicability of large PWR know how to LW-SMR, the postulated sequences calculated with Lumped Parameter (LP) codes were used in previous work [7] as a screening exercise to identify how LW-SMR specific phenomena required targeted upgrades of the *containmentFOAM* model library. *ContainmentFOAM* is a CFD toolbox—developed at Forschungszentrum Jülich as an add-on for OpenFOAM (currently v11)—with a modelling basis originally consolidated for the phenomenology prevailing in dry large-PWR containments. It is focused on multi-species transport and condensation-driven heat transfer and aiming at technical-scale safety analyses. Among the different upgrading needs, the stronger coupling between the containment atmosphere and the Pressure Suppression System (PSS) motivated the main development effort, since the transport and accumulation of non-condensables at the PSS is the driving phenomenon for the containment pressurisation. A fully high-fidelity, two-phase CFD representation of containment and PSS was discarded, as it would be computationally prohibitive. The proposed solution was a multi-fidelity coupling framework where *containmentFOAM* resolves the containment space while the PSS is treated at system level, with data exchanged through an Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) based coupling to OpenModelica [7]. This coupling was validated against experiments with comparable coupled phenomena and tested with a preliminary application at the technical scale [7,8].

Within SASPAM-SA, most partners rely on LP SA codes (MELCOR, ASTEC, AC2) with empirical models to replicate the severe accident phenomenology at an affordable computational cost for simulating transients of several days. Within SASPAM-SA, *containmentFOAM*'s role was to complement those calculations with high-fidelity, 3D insights into the containment response of Design II for selected time windows. The objective of the present work is not to replace the LP analyses, but to identify and simulate phases of the SASPAM-SA sequences where local heterogeneities, not resolved in 0D/1D models, can become safety-relevant. In particular, the 3D transport and accumulation of non-condensable gases (N_2 and H_2) to the PSS. Following this scope, Section 2 introduces the selected SASPAM-SA transient and defines the two analysed time windows, Section 3 presents the Design II *containmentFOAM* model, and Section 4 discusses the results for the blowdown phase (Section 4.1) and for the later phase dominated by hydrogen transport (Section 4.2).

2. SEVERE ACCIDENT TIME WINDOWS FROM SASPAM-SA SEQUENCES

SASPAM-SA Design-II is a generic ~300 MWe integral PWR concept with a dry, inertised containment integrating several passive safety systems, including a PSS coupled to the drywell. This section is intended to describe the main characteristics of the SASPAM-SA Design-II SA postulated sequences simulated with SA codes, which will be necessary to better understand the containment analyses that will be presented in Section 4. A more comprehensive description of the Design Basis Accident (DBA) and all the SA postulated in SASPAM are available in [9] and [6,10], respectively.

For the response the DBA (Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) break) the different systems—Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV- P_1), Containment/Drywell (P_2) and PSS (P_3)—are expected to behave as a closely coupled thermal-hydraulic system driven by natural circulation. In the initial pressure-suppression stage (see Figure 1, containing all the needed acronyms), ADS actuation rapidly couples the RPV and containment pressures, limiting the coolant inventory discharged thanks to the faster pressure equalization ($P_1 = P_2$). The resulting pressure rise in the drywell promotes venting to the PSS, where steam is efficiently condensed in the subcooled pool and the pressure increase becomes dominated by the progressive accumulation of non-

condensables in the PSS gas space. After the drywell peak, P_1 and P_2 decrease due to primary-side cooling and wall condensation, and since P_3 decreases more slowly the pressure gradient then reverses ($P_3 > P_2$), pushing water from the PSS into the drywell and flooding the reactor cavity. When the cavity water level rises above the break elevation, the long-term cooling loop is closed and stable cooling is established (right sketch in Figure 1), with the coupled system approaching $P_1 \approx P_2 \approx P_3$ while decay heat is removed by the passive Emergency Heat Removal System (EHRS).

As already concluded at [10], SASPAM-SA confirmed that the pivotal safety system was the EHRS (the combined failure of all the other safety systems still resulted in a successful long-term cooling of the core). Therefore, SASPAM-SA sequences combined the failure of the EHRS with additional safety systems (ADS-Automatic Depressurization System, LGMS-Long Term Gravity Make-up System, EBT-Emergency Borated Tank) [6]. From the containment-analysis perspective, one evident time window to investigate is the blowdown phase, since the SA codes predict a pressure increase above 11 bar during the first 1000 s. In this early transient, containment phenomenology is dominant: wall condensation rates and the transport of non-condensable gases to the PSS are expected to be at their maximum. And evaluation of the 3D flows should also confirm the nearly homogeneous containment conditions usually assumed for blowdown, or whether the coupling with the PSS can still generate safety-relevant local heterogeneities. In addition, the rapid evolution of the containment conditions is reinforced by ADS actuation, which motivated the selection of the SA sequence including ADS-1 actuation (SA3). Figure 2 summarizes the corresponding pressure evolution (P_1 , P_2 and P_3), the main system actuations, and the associated phenomenological windows.

A second time window of interest was selected between 30,000 s and 50,000 s, at the beginning of the core-degradation phase (between PhW2 and PhW3 in Figure 2). In this period, after the first Filtered Containment Venting System (FCVS) actuation, core oxidation starts and hydrogen is released to the containment. With the ADS-1 valve open, the more elevated release favours the hydrogen stratification. The potential 3D heterogeneities can affect hydrogen transport to the PSS and the non-condensable distribution, which in turn influence steam condensation and containment pressure evolution. A proper prediction of the pressure response in this phase is particularly relevant because it is linked to the observed FCVS cycling in Figure 2, and therefore to the timing of venting actions and the associated source-term evolution.

Figure 1. On the left, 3D CAD representation of Design-II containment. The additional 2D sketches represent the status of passive safety tanks in different stages of DBA and SA

Figure 2. P_1 , P_2 and P_3 pressure evolution for the selected SA with colour codes for phenomena windows. The figure is produced and table is adapted from the work of Sapienza University of Rome [11]

3. SASPAM-SA DESIGN-II containmentFOAM MODEL

The CFD model is based on the geometry shown on the left of Figure 1. The containment consists of a steel shell with an inner diameter of about 25 m and an upper removable head for outage requirements. Compared with conventional large-PWR containments, the internal layout is simpler and less compartmentalised. According to the available design information, the containment should be evaluated as two main halves with different pressure evolutions, separated by a concrete floor: an upper half containing the RPV, QT, LGMS and EBT, and a lower half containing the PSS tanks, connected to the upper region through the vent lines.

The geometric information was taken from the common SASPAM-SA database developed as reference input for the LP analyses [12]. Since the level of detail required for a 3D CFD model is significantly higher than for a 0D control-volume representation, missing geometric data had to be completed by engineering judgement. This process led to a detailed CAD model of Design-II, which was then used as the basis for the *containmentFOAM* model, and also helped identify and correct inconsistencies in the initial geometry database used by the LP modellers. To preserve consistency with the SA-code models, the final 3D geometry was checked against the common database, yielding relative deviations below 1.2% for free volume and 2.8% for wall surface. Minor adaptations were then introduced to facilitate meshing, the main ones being a local modification of vent-line thickness, and the non-inclusion of the feed and main steam lines.

The containment model was subdivided into three regions: the containment gas space (FLUID), the concrete cavity (CONCRETE), and the containment shell (STEEL). As shown in Figure 3, a hybrid meshing strategy was adopted: automatic unstructured meshes were used for the FLUID and CONCRETE domains, while the STEEL was kept as a block-structured hexahedral mesh. The FLUID domain was discretised with 2.3 million predominantly hexahedral cells using cfMesh (cut-cell approach with cubic base cells), with a base cell size of 0.4 m and up to two local refinement levels (0.2 and 0.1 m) around relevant geometric features (e.g., vent lines, QT and LGMS), as illustrated in Figure 3. The CONCRETE region was meshed with about 0.37 million unstructured cells (cfMesh), whereas the STEEL was represented by a block-structured mesh of about 0.36 million hexahedral cells generated with ICEM. Wall condensation was only modelled on the concrete surfaces and on the STEEL shell, with all other internal structures treated as adiabatic. Boundary-layer resolution was applied on condensing walls (Figure 3), with average y^+ below 2, while thicker near-wall layers were accepted on non-condensing adiabatic structures due to less restrictive wall functions without condensation. For the FLUID mesh, the main quality indicators were satisfactory for the present calculations (maximum skewness 1.18, maximum non-orthogonality 55 with average ≈ 5 , average cell volume ratio 0.85). A formal mesh sensitivity analysis was, however, not yet performed.

Figure 3. Hybrid meshing: structured steel-shell mesh and unstructured fluid/concrete meshes

The ‘baseline model set’ for *containmentFOAM* technical scale analysis, which was intensively validated before (e.g., [8,13–15]), was employed. Its main characteristics are summarized and described in Table I. Essentially, it finds on a single-phase simplification of the containment atmosphere, where wall condensation is modeled using a diffusion layer approach [16] and bulk condensation a homogeneous equilibrium model [17]. Solids use a simpler approach only solving for the energy equation to represent heat diffusion. All structures allowing condensation are represented by a conjugate heat transfer (CHT) approach.

A key enabling element of the present model is the *containmentFOAM*-OpenModelica multi-fidelity coupling implemented through the FMI-2 standard, where the containment is resolved in 3D CFD and the PSS is represented by a system-level model exchanged as an Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU). The main rationale for using OpenModelica was its flexibility and the availability of reusable components and modelling libraries that can be readily adapted to the needs of the coupling. FMI then provides a code-agnostic framework for information exchange and coupled simulation. This approach was introduced and validated in previous work [7], so only the main hypotheses of the PSS-FMU are recalled here: the PSS is represented by a lumped 0D two-phase single-node model with complete steam condensation into a subcooled pool, non-condensable bypass of the pool, user-defined heat transfer coefficients, and no pool-surface evaporation. PPOOLEX was selected as validation benchmark because it also involves a containment and a pressure-suppression pool with two closely coupled gas spaces, where the pressure evolution is strongly driven by non-condensable transport. For the evaluated PPOOLEX tests, the validation demonstrated both qualitative and quantitative accuracy of the coupling framework. The impact of the PSS-FMU simplifications, mostly the neglected evaporation, on the present Design-II calculations is discussed in the Results section.

The boundary conditions were taken from the MELCOR calculations for SASPAM-SA Design-II provided by Sapienza University of Rome (UniRoma) and detailed in [6]. Three injection sources were considered in the CFD model (the two sides of the DVI break and the ADS-1 discharge above the QT). For each source, the release rate, composition and temperature were directly imposed from the MELCOR injection tables. Steam, hydrogen and enthalpy releases were applied as volumetric sources (order of 1 m³), with a simplified averaged representation of directional momentum.

Table I. Physical Models (adapted from [18])

Physics	Model
governing equations	Unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations, total energy equation, transport equation for species mass fraction
turbulent transport	k- ω based Shear Stress Transport (SST) model, including production and dissipation terms for buoyancy based on SGDH; Turbulent heat and mass transport: SGDH, $Pr_t=Sc_t=0.85$
multi-species transport	Ideal mixture approach. Each individual set of gas transport, properties (heat capacity, viscosity, conductivity) is implemented by tables, being temperature dependent for H ₂ and N ₂ , and pressure and temperature dependant for H ₂ O. Effective binary diffusion model with pressure and temperature diffusion coefficients (Fuller model)
wall treatment and condensation	<u>Wall condensation</u> : single phase ‘diffusion-layer’ approach, continuous wall functions
thermal radiation	P ₁ model, gray participating mixture, ($\kappa_{H_2O}=10 \text{ bar}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$, NCG transparent), $\epsilon_{\text{wall}} = 0.6$
system models	PSS: Single node lumped two phase model built with OpenModelica. Complete condensation of steam into subcooled water, and no surface evaporation

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

4.1. SASPAM-SA3: Blowdown phase

For the blowdown case, the set-up illustrated in Figure 4 preserves the same modelling basis introduced in Section 3. The PSS coupling is treated implicitly through the FMI interface located at the end of the vent lines. There, *containmentFOAM* provides the local pressure, temperature and gas composition at the outlet patch, and the OpenModelica PSS FMU returns the mass flow rate imposed at the CFD boundary as a function of the counter-pressure (water column plus non-condensables in the PSS gas space). In addition, Figure 4 shows the three release locations (DVI-1, DVI-2 and ADS-1) and flow rates used for the blowdown. For the DVI break sources, MELCOR’s liquid discharge (initially at 155 bar) cannot be injected directly into the single-phase CFD containment model, which is at near-atmospheric conditions. Therefore, an isenthalpic expansion correction was applied to estimate the available energy for flashing liquid into a steam flow for *containmentFOAM* (from the LP-code break conditions to the CFD saturation conditions).

Figure 4. Sketch of case set-up: FMI coupling, location and flow rate of volume sources, and mesh regions

A constant time-step strategy was adopted to improve the stability of the FMI coupling in this first time window, starting from $\Delta t=0.001$ s and increasing up to 0.003 s toward the end of the transient. The calculations were run on 96 cores, with a wall-clock time of about 140 h (13 440 core-h), which corresponds to roughly 170 s of simulated transient per day. The time step control kept the maximum CFL number below 2, with a maximum of 5 outer PIMPLE iterations and all residuals below 10^{-4} (generally below 10^{-5}). It should also be noted that the highest local velocities of the blowdown are not fully represented because the releases are imposed as volumetric sources (not surface/patch injections). However, these very fast transients remains a challenge for high fidelity codes, and the authors are not aware of comparable CFD simulations of the containment blowdown phase in the open literature.

Figure 5 compares the blowdown results from MELCOR, the *containmentFOAM* base case, and a parametric *containmentFOAM* case with modified energy transfer from the PSS liquid to the PSS gas (“colder PSS”), just included to complement the interpretation of the results. The four graphs are shown together to support a consistent reading of the blowdown response. In fact, although the global containment-pressure evolution remains comparable between cases, other quantities that are usually considered relevant in containment analyses (e.g., wall condensation and transport to the PSS) can differ significantly.

Before ADS-1 actuation (≈ 200 s), the *containmentFOAM* base case reproduces the MELCOR pressure increase with good qualitative and quantitative agreement. After ADS-1 opens, both curves keep a similar trend but progressively diverge, reaching at 1000 s about 1.2 MPa in MELCOR and about 1.4 MPa in the *containmentFOAM* base case. This difference is not straightforward to interpret from the other graphs, since the CFD/FMU calculation predicts both higher steel-liner condensation and higher transport to the PSS,

Figure 5. MELCOR (UniRoma) vs *containmentFOAM* blowdown calculations comparison

which would a priori suggest a lower containment pressure. The key point is that the additional transport to the PSS is largely associated with steam (which condenses in the pool), while the transported nitrogen inventory (not shown here) is comparatively similar. Therefore, the understanding of the pressure evolution should be mainly based on the higher gas temperature in the PSS gas space predicted by the OpenModelica PSS model, which increases the PSS counter-pressure and, consequently, the containment pressure.

This interpretation motivated the parametric “colder PSS” case, where the effective heat-transfer coefficient (including natural convection and evaporation effects) used in the PSS FMU in all PPOOLEX validation experiments was increased from 30 to 130 W/m² K. The latter value was estimated just to replicate the MELCOR PSS gas temperature evolution, and not as a realistic figure. As shown in Figure 5, this adjustment strongly reduces the difference in PSS gas temperature after ADS-1 actuation (peak values of about 185 °C in the base case, versus about 110 °C in MELCOR and in the colder-PSS case), and the containment pressure correspondingly moves much closer to MELCOR (at 1000 s, from about 1.4 MPa in the base case to about 1.28 MPa, compared with about 1.2 MPa in MELCOR). Having closer backpressures from the PSS, allowed to investigate how the pressure equalization affected the containment phenomena. Interestingly, the wall-condensation curve and the transport-to-PSS flow rates remain of the same order as in the base case, which reinforces that the improved pressure comparability is mainly linked to the PSS gas-space conditions, rather than to changes in the main containment-side mechanisms. The remaining code-to-code differences are still under investigation and cannot be resolved further with the currently available comparison data.

Regarding 3D effects, no additional plots are included at this sub section because the containment atmosphere is mostly homogeneous after ADS-1 actuation. The present minor heterogeneities —see the asymmetry seen in Figure 5 for the flow rates to PSS-N (North) and PSS-S (South) in the base case— indicate some 3D influence on the transport processes, but no safety-relevant impact on the global blowdown response. Overall, for the blowdown time window, the results indicate that the pressure build-up is mainly controlled by the state of the non-condensables accumulated in the PSS gas space (especially N₂ inventory and gas temperature). So, as an insight for LP codes, the detailed representation of PSS physics seems to be more influential than a more detailed 3D resolution (or complex nodalization) of the containment atmosphere.

4.2. SASPAM-SA3: Late phase with hydrogen transport

Similarly to Section 4.1, the evaluation of the second time window of interest is introduced by presenting a sketch of the case set-up (Figure 6). Apart from the evident variation of the mass source flow rates, now also including the hydrogen mass flow rate in a secondary axis, one clear visual difference is that now the cavity is mostly occupied by water, which has been included in the model to actuate as an additional condensing surface. To keep the single-phase approach, the water pool is represented by a thin solid region that allows the water surface to reach the containment steam saturation temperature while the bulk is maintained at the liquid temperature estimated by MELCOR. However, the main difference with the previous case set-up is the replacement of the FMU-FMI coupling by a pressure boundary condition representing the containment pressure predicted by MELCOR. This replacement was motivated by preliminary tests showing that, in this late window, the simplified PSS-FMU (without pool-surface evaporation) lead to unphysically high flow rates from the containment to the PSS. Due to this limitation —combined with 100% steam in the containment: conditions beyond the current validation basis of the FMU— the PSS pressure can only increase by the heat transferred by a hotter water pool, and not by the increasing steam partial pressure. Consequently, the missing steam build-up in the PSS gas space was artificially compensated by excessive steam/enthalpy transport to heat up the pool and pressurise the PSS gas. Therefore, a MELCOR pressure boundary was imposed to evaluate the effect of 3D transport vs the MELCOR reference data under equivalent pressures.

The time step control followed the same criteria described in Section 4.1, but with significantly larger time steps due to the lower velocities of this time window. The time step was automatically adjusted to keep the maximum CFL below 1, typically reaching ≈ 0.008 - 0.01 s. The calculation was run on 256 cores of FZJ's

high performance computing facility JURECA, and advanced about 1550 s of transient per day. This corresponds to about 12.9 days of wall-clock time (≈ 310 h), i.e., approximately 80 000 core-h.

Figure 6. Sketch of case set-up: Outlet pressure, location and flow rate of volume sources, and mesh regions

To assess the hydrogen distribution and its transport from the containment to the PSS during PhW2-3, two complementary types of results are presented. First, Figure 7 compares *containmentFOAM* and MELCOR by means of two global variables: (i) the containment averaged hydrogen volume fraction; and (ii) the integral mass transported from the containment to the PSS, shown separately for steam and hydrogen. Then, to interpret the origin of the differences in these global trends, Figure 8 provides selected 3D CFD visualizations of the identified heterogeneities, focusing on the temperature field and on the hydrogen distribution in the upper containment and at the vent line connecting containment and PSS. The plotting times of Figure 8 are chosen to highlight the heterogeneities.

Figure 7. MELCOR (UniRoma) vs *containmentFOAM* hydrogen distribution comparison

Figure 7 shows that both calculations predict a similar global build-up of hydrogen, with *containmentFOAM* consistently higher and reaching 11.1% at the end of the transient, compared with 10.1% in MELCOR. At the same time, the integral steam and hydrogen mass transported to the PSS is lower in *containmentFOAM*. A more complete interpretation of this LP-CFD comparison (including wall condensation rates and gas temperature) is currently being performed. However, even with that information, a consolidated quantitative explanation of the code-to-code differences has not yet been reached yet. In principle, since both codes use the same mass sources and *containmentFOAM* reproduces the MELCOR pressure evolution, the lower transport to the PSS should imply higher wall-condensation rates in *containmentFOAM*, but this point cannot yet be demonstrated rigorously with the currently available MELCOR output and will require further exchanges with UniRoma.

Even if any interpretation should remain qualitative, Figure 7 and Figure 8 show that the containment conditions are no longer homogeneous, unlike the blowdown phase of Section 4.1. Figure 7 indicates a clear asymmetry in the transport to PSS-N and PSS-S, especially for steam during the first part of the window. The non-integrated mass-flow data (not shown here) confirmed that the dominant vent line changes during the transient. Figure 8 represents the heterogeneities behind these differences. The temperature field exhibits a vertical stratification, with the upper region hotter than the lower one and top-to-bottom differences reaching up to about 40 °C, with the stratification growing as the transient progresses. The hydrogen field shows a similar behaviour, with higher volume fractions in the upper containment and different hydrogen concentrations at the two vent-line entrances. These heterogeneities are sufficient to create different conditions in the flow transported to PSS-N and/or PSS-S.

It is important to underline that this analysis remains limited by the simple outlets based on MELCOR's pressure used at the CFD side. The lack of a PSS model able to store and track the effects of the different mass and composition histories coming from each side does not allow to evaluate the feedback of these heterogeneities on the thermodynamic state of each PSS gas space. Improving the current analysis will require a more advanced PSS model, with a modelling basis able to represent the relevant PSS physics and evaluating the impact of the identified 3D differences into a quantitative system response.

Figure 8. Insights on the identified 3D heterogeneities for the simulations of PhW2 time window

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work, developed in the framework of SASPAM-SA, moved from the conceptual exploration of *containmentFOAM* application to LW-SMR severe-accident analysis —identifying on the way a list of model development needs— to the technical scale safety evaluation presented in this work. The main enabling step was the implementation of the *containmentFOAM*-OpenModelica multi-fidelity coupling, which allowed the containment response and the PSS feedback to be simulated in a coupled manner at an affordable computational cost. Within this framework, two complementary time windows (PhW1 and PhW3) were analysed for SASPAM-SA Design-II: the fast-changing blowdown case, which is particularly demanding for CFD in terms of stability and computational cost, and a later hydrogen-transport window, closer to the original modelling basis of *containmentFOAM*. Despite the known limitations of the current set-up (discussed below), the blowdown calculation with flashing correction and coupled PSS feedback constitutes a relevant step forward with respect to the current open literature on CFD containment analyses.

The role of CFD analysis in SASPAM-SA is to complement the integral calculations of LP codes, with the objective of identifying when 3D effects add safety-relevant information and when simpler representations are sufficient. In this sense, the two analysed windows provide different messages:

- Blowdown window (PhW1): the CFD results confirm that the containment atmosphere rapidly evolves towards nearly homogeneous conditions after ADS-1 actuation. The observed 3D heterogeneities are limited and do not appear to produce a significant safety-relevant impact on the global blowdown response. For this phase, the results indicate that the dominant modelling challenge is not the 3D containment resolution itself, but the adequate representation of the PSS response, since the pressure evolution is mainly controlled by the species partial pressures in the PSS gas space (inventory, composition, and temperature).
- Late hydrogen-transport window (PhW3): *containmentFOAM* predicted a non-homogeneous distribution of temperature and gas composition at different points of this 20.000 second window characterised by low momentum sources and buoyancy driven flows. The heterogeneities induced differences in the mass and composition of each containment-PSS vent lines. However, the quantitative impact of the heterogeneities could not be quantified since the CFD domain is closed by a MELCOR-based pressure outlet and not by a PSS model able to store and evolve the different mass and composition histories reaching each PSS. Whether these heterogeneities accumulate or compensate each other in the actual PSS response remains to be evaluated.

Therefore, the current limiting factor of the multi-fidelity framework is the simplified physics of the PSS FMU. The PSS model was initially conceived mainly as a computationally efficient system-level closure providing counter-pressure feedback to the *containmentFOAM* high-fidelity model. However, in the present Design-II applications, its simplification of the physics, particularly the too simple modelling of the pool surface heat and mass transfer, proved to be a limiting factor for the global accuracy of the analyses. Therefore, the priority to advance these first application of *containmentFOAM* to LW-SMR safety analysis —where our CFD toolbox even proved its ability to simulate a blowdown— is to extend the current PSS FMU modelling basis and, in parallel, to investigate similar couplings with validated established codes.

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